

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FOOD PLANTS OF THE GARAGUSH MOUNTAIN AREA

Novruzi Nurlana

PhD in Biology Science,

Nakhchivan Teachers Institution, Head Teacher Position,

Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

ORCHID ID: 0000-0002-3712-2111

Abstract

The Garagush mountain system is one of the highest peaks of the Deralayaz range. It has an absolute height of 1200-2600 m. Based on the long-term research conducted in the Garagush mountain area, it has been clarified that medicinal, alkaloid, vitamin, resinous, rubbery, ethereal, citrus, nutritious, nectar-rich, dye and vaccine-rich, as well as decorative and fodder plants are widely distributed in the existing vegetation here. Among such useful plants, plants that provide nectar and pollen are not only a natural resource, but also an inexhaustible source of resources.

Keywords: Garagush Mountain, wild vegetable plants, honey-producing plants, *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh., *Zosima absinthifolia* (Vent.) Link, *Prangos acaulis* (DC.) Bornm.

Introduction: The Garagush mountain system is one of the highest peaks of the Daralayaz range. It has an absolute height of 1200-2600 m. Garagush Mountain is located between the upper reaches of the Qabaglichay River and the village of Chalkhangala, south of the Kecheltepe Mountain. On the eastern side of Garagush Mountain, small streams formed by spring and snow water along the valleys merge to form the Lizbirt River. On the northern side, there is Khanbulagi and the Billavachay River formed by many small springs. Garagush Mountain, one of the branches of the Daralayaz range, is divided into valleys with steep slopes. Mountain-meadow steppe soils prevail in the territory of Garagush Mountain. The vegetation of the area is adapted to this altitude and temperature. Here, desert and semi-desert, phrygana, gariga, forest and shrubland, mountain xerophyte, subalpine meadows and tall grass, petrophilous (rock-debris) vegetation type, meadow, shrubland and mixed woodlands are grouped. Starting from early spring, one plant species replaces another in the territory of Mount Garagush. Annual rhizomatous, bulbous plants and a number of perennial herbs develop rapidly in the area, bloom and form seeds.

Based on the long-term research conducted in the territory of Mountain Garagush, it has been clarified that medicinal, alkaloid, vitamin, resinous, rubbery, ethereal, citrus, nutritious, nectar-rich, dye and vaccine plants, as well as decorative and fodder plants are widely distributed in the existing vegetation here. Among such useful plants, plants that produce nectar and pollen are not only a natural resource, but also an inexhaustible source of resources. Their more detailed study, discovery and provision for public use are one of the urgent issues of the time.

Wheat, a strategic crop, is considered a priority crop for any country in terms of ensuring food security at a time when the world population is constantly increasing, general urbanization processes are intensifying, and global climate changes are occurring. The above-mentioned factors have led to a doubling of the

world population's demand for agricultural products in the last 30 years. As a result, wheat production in the world has exceeded 620 million tons in the last five years. These successes have occurred due to the achievements made in the field of wheat breeding. In the last 25 years, wheat production in the world has increased by 100 million tons due to new varieties created through breeding [13, p. 6-47]. According to literature data, *Triticum araraticum* Jakubz. and *Triticum durum* Desf. wheat species existed wild in the territory of Garagush Mountain. However, since these species were not found during our research, they were included in the taxonomic spectrum of the area based on literature data.

Wild vegetable plants growing in the territory of Garagush Mountain are collected and widely used by the population. Starting from early spring, *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh., *Zosima absinthifolia* (Vent.) Link, *Prangos acaulis* (DC.) Bornm., *Coriandrum sativum* L., *Bifora radians* Bieb., *Chaerophyllum crinitum* Boiss., *Rheum ribes* L., *Rumex acetosella* L. and *R. acetosa* L., etc. are collected. At the same time, the population also collects medicinal plants and these plants are used in folk medicine. Especially thyme and yarrow species are collected more abundantly. These plants are used in the form of infusions.

In the desert vegetation of the Garagush Mountain, we find the following wild vegetable plants: *Scorzonera rigida* Aucher ex DC., *Capsella bursa - pastoris* (L.) Medik., *Chenopodium album* L., *Ch. foliosum* Aschers., *Spinacia tetrandra* Stev., *Salicornia europaea* L., *Atriplex turcomanica* (Moq.) Boiss., *Polygonum aviculare* L.

Semi-desert vegetation is mainly distributed in the foothill zone, at altitudes of 1000-1200 m above sea level. Wild vegetable plants have formed many groups in this vegetation type. According to the conducted studies, wild vegetable plants in semi-desert vegetation are represented by species such as *Capparis spinosa* L. (*C. herbacea* Willd.), *Achillea tenuifolia* Lam., *Allium rubellum* Bieb. (*A. syntamantum* C.Koch), *Scorzonera rigida* Aucher ex DC., *Geranium tuberosum* L.,

Eryngium campestre L., *Atriplex tatarica* L. (A. *araz-dajanica* Kapell.), *Chenopodium strictum* Roth.

Mountain xerophyte (firgana) vegetation is zonal in nature. Plants belonging to this type are mainly distributed at an altitude of 1200-1500 m. Wild vegetable plants belonging to this type, such as *Prangos acaulis* (DC.) Bornm., *Capparis spinosa* L. (C. *herbacea* Willd.), *Allium atroviolaceum* Boiss. (A. *firnotunicatum* Fomin.), *A. rubellum* Bieb. (A. *syntamanthum* C.Koch), etc., are part of various formations and associations of mountain xerophyte vegetation.

Steppe vegetation covers an altitude of 1500-2300 m. The vegetation includes *Teucrium chamaedrys* L., *Eryngium caucasicum* Trautv., *Ziziphora tenuior* L., *Echinops sphaerocephalus* L. (E. *dagestanicus* Iljin; E. *erevanensis* Mulk.), *Taraxacum officinale* Wigg., etc. species.

In forest and shrub vegetation types, wild vegetable plants grow mainly in forest glades and at the bottom of bushes. Forests cover an altitude of 1650 - 2450 m, and shrubs - 1200-2500 m. In forest and shrub vegetation types, wild vegetable plants *Ornithogalum brachystachys* C.Koch., *Rumex acetosella* L. (R. *multifidus* L.), *Filago vulgaris* Lam., *Scorzonera latifolia* (Fisch. & C.A. Mey.) DC. and *Malva sylvestris* L. predominate.

The meadow vegetation type covers almost all altitudinal belts in terms of vertical zonation. It consists of understory, post-forest meadow-shrub and subalpine meadows. In this vegetation, *Filago vulgaris* Lam., *Tragopogon graminifolius* DC., *T. latifolius* Boiss., *Potentilla reptans* L., *Taraxacum officinale* Wigg., *Scorzonera rigida* Aucher ex DC., *Vicia anatolica* Turrill, *Mentha longifolia* (L.) Huds., *Rumex acetosa* L., etc. species are widespread. A number of species of the genera hemlock and yarrow constitute tall grasses.

Rock and scree vegetation covers all mountainous belts. In this vegetation type, wild vegetable plants include *Bifora radians* Bieb., *Chaerophyllum crinitum* Boiss., *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh. [F. *sioides* (Wib.) Asch.], *Rumex acetosa* L., *Oxyria digyna* (L.) Hill., *Allium schoenoprasum* L., *Urtica dioica* L., etc. species.

The types of plants that produce nectar and pollen in the vegetation of the Garagush Mountain area and their potential for use in beekeeping have also been extensively studied. In the Garagush Mountain area, *Aster* L., *Rosa* L., *Astragalus* L., *Barbarea* R.Br., *Centaurea* L., *Cephalaria* Schrad. ex Roem. & Schult., *Cerasus* Mill., *Cirsium* Hill., *Crataegus* L., *Dianthus* L., *Dracocephalum* L., *Thymus* L., *Echinops* L., *Echium* L., *Epilobium* L., *Eryngium* L., *Galium* L., *Geranium* L., *Lonicera* L., *Lotus* L., *Marrubium* L., *Melilotus* Hill., *Mentha* L., *Nepeta* L., *Onobrychis* Hill., *Potentilla* L., *Prunella* L., *Ranunculus* L., *Rhamnus* L., *Salix* L., *Salvia* L., *Sideritis* L., *Campanula* L., *Symphytum* L., *Teucrium* L., *Trifolium* L., *Verbascum* L., *Vicia* L., *Viola* L. genera dominate.

The vegetation formed at the north-western foot of the Garagush mountain is mainly mountain-xerophyte vegetation, which is found as a dominant vegetation type in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, especially in the middle mountain belt. Here *Astracantha microcephala* (Willd.) Podelch, *Festuca valesiaca*

Gaudin, *Stipa capillata* L., *Elitrigia trichophora* (Link) Nevski, *Trisetum flavescens* (L.) Beauv., *Astragalus regelii* Trautv., *Onobrychis transcaucasica* Grossh., *Coluteocarpus vesicaria* (L.) Holmboe, *Prangos acaulis* (DC.) Bornm., *Ferula persica* Willd., *Medicago caerulea* Less. ex Ledeb., and from the varieties *Centaurea szovitsiana* Boiss., *Ziziphora biebersteiniana* Grossh., *Senecio vernalis* Waldst. do Kit. attracts attention. These species form the basis of the food base in beekeeping until the end of summer and mid-summer. Among the geophytes found here, species belonging to the genera *Iris* L., *Merandera Ramond*, *Gagea* Salisb, *Tulipa* L., *Allium* L., *Ixiolirion* Herb., *Bellevalia* Lapeyr., *Muscari* Mill., *Leontice* L., etc., which also bloom and produce seeds in early spring, the leaves and stem dry out, and the bulbs are protected under the soil. As early spring plants, bees can use them within a short time [15].

This vegetation type has a unique species composition, indicator and dominant plants. *Daphne transcaucasica* Pobed., *Zygophyllum atriplicoides* Fisch. et C.A. Mey., *Zygophyllum fabago* L., *Astragalus lagurus* Willd., *Atraphaxis spinosa* L., *Acanthophyllum pungens* (Bunge) Boiss., *Acanthophyllum mucronatum* C.A. Mey., *Onobrychis cornuta* (L.) Desv., *Thymus kotschyanus* Boiss. et Hohen., *Teucrium polium* L., *Michauxia laevigata* Vent., *Gundelia tournefortii* L. are among the species of this group. Almost the majority of these species are found in the shallow valleys and slopes formed by the Khanbulagi and other springs at the foot of the Karagush Ghagi. This vegetation type plays an important role as a feed base for beekeeping.

The forest-shrub vegetation spreads at heights of 1500-2200 m above the sea level of Karagush mountain and rises to the borders of the subalpine zone. Here, *Ephedra procera* Fisch. et C.A. May., *Lonicera iberica* Boiss. et Buhse, *Rhamnus pallasii* Fisch. et C.A. Mey., *Crataegus caucasica* C. Koch, *Juniperus excelsa* subsp. polycarpus (C. Koch) Takht., *Rosa canina* L., *Berberis vulgaris* L., *Sorbus graeca* (Spach) Lodd. ex Schauer, *Cotoneaster melanocarpus* Fisch. et Blytt, *Pistacia mutica* Fisch. et C.A. Mey., *Amelanchier ovalis* Medik., *Amygdalus fenzliana* (Fritsch) Lipsky, *Tamarix meyeri* Boiss., *Tamarix hohenackeri* Bunge, etc. types are found. As can be seen, there is a sufficient food base for bees in forest and shrub vegetation.

Material and methods: The research area covers the territory of the Garagush Mountain of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Research has been conducted on the study of food-important species and vegetation of this area, collection and preservation of materials. For this purpose, since 2019, expeditions have been made to the area in 10 directions in the spring, summer and autumn seasons. Starting from the semi-stationary, more than 100 geobotanical notes and herbariums on the species composition and structure of plants were taken, and their individual photographs were taken. During the research, classical and modern botanical - floristic, systematic, ecological, areological, phytocenological, plant resources and statistical methods were used.

The range of plants and their geographical elements are given according to A.A. Grossheim

[25;26;27], N.N. Portenier [35]. Measurement of experimental areas was carried out with the "Laser distance meter Telescope" TOMSHCO TM 1000A device.

The specification of systematic taxa was carried out on the basis of the International Code of Botanical Nomenclature, Angiosperm Phylogeny Group (APG I, II, III, IV) [37; 38; 39; 40] and Pteridophyte Phylogeny Group - PPG I.

The life forms of plants were classified according to I.G. Serebryakov [33, pp. 38-92; 34, pp. 146-205] and C.R. Raunkier [41], the types, classes and groups of the area were classified according to A.A. Grossheim [25; 26; 27] and N.N. Portenier [35, pp. 26-33] and separate research works.

Results and discussion: Thus, the food and medicinal species growing in the mentioned vegetation areas of the Garagush Mountain are currently collected by the population. Various dishes, teas, infusions are prepared with these plants. Also, since the flowering phases of the plants mentioned in the area are intermittent at an altitude of 800-2600 m above sea level, the bee colonies kept here can be continuously supplied with pollen and nectar. Therefore, it is advisable to keep about a thousand bee colonies in this zone. Studying them in more detail, revealing them and making them available to the public is one of the urgent issues of the time.

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